

MEANS OF COMPRESSION IN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETING

Ibragimova Dilnora Shavkat qizi

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

2nd. year Master's student of the Department of Interpretation

E-mail: ibragimovadilnora38@gmail.com

ANNOTATION

Simultaneous interpreting for all intents and purposes is a particularly common interpreting modality that kind of is utilized in conferences, place of business education sessions, and prison or authorities situations in a fairly big way. In the instance of simultaneous interpreting, the interpreter goes thru a three-part simultaneous process: Listening to the original language the speaker cognitively converts the verbal exchange into the generally goal language earlier than decoding it to the third party/audience in the for all intents and purposes goal language, actually contrary to popular belief. This actually is achieved similtaneously as the speaker continues to essentially provide their speech, which particularly is why simultaneous deciphering takes fairly such a for all intents and purposes high diploma of brain and focus, really contrary to popular belief.

Keywords: *simultaneous interpretation, Syllabic compression, Lexical compression, Syntactic compression, Situational compression.*

Introduction

Compression is a one of a kind type of transformation that is based totally on the immanent properties of the language device and contributes to bringing prolonged syntactic constructions to a less complex form, which, however, can transmit the same amount of information as full accelerated constructions. Compression in simultaneous translation is traditionally regarded in as one of the skill of making sure the very opportunity of this type of translation undertaking and is defined as “saving speech and language ability for expressing the same content”.¹

As a capacity of measuring the degree of compression in simultaneous translation (ST), a evaluation of the syllabic value of the output message (translation textual content – TT) with the syllabic value of the unique message (source textual content – ST) is used. A.F. Shiryaev defines speech compression as follows: “The approach of decreasing the volume of a message besides causing vast damage to the undertaking that the speaker sets himself is called compression (speech compression)” (p.83)

¹ Belloch, G. 2001. 'Introduction to Data Compression'.

I.I Poluyan¹ pretty rightly notes that, in relation to simultaneous translation, it is hardly possible to speak about compression of the output message, seeing that the output message does not but exist in its finished form throughout the operation of a simultaneous interpreter. In connection with the expansion of the scope of simultaneous translation in the remaining three many years compared to the previous duration of unique relevance used to be the query of how to put in force compression in ST, about the assets of speech compression in translation. Decision this trouble would make a contribution to a widespread optimization of the translation process in phrases of the time of acceptance of the translation solutions, saving the efforts of translators, improving the exceptional of translation. This query is additionally important for didactics of translation: understanding of possible resources compression in the joint undertaking and strategies for its implementation would permit orient future simultaneous interpreters to enhance skills, essential for the implementation of simultaneous translation in such a way in a manner that prevents the interpreter from lagging too far behind speaker and unreasonable omissions of relevant statistics and at the same time saves the intellectual efforts of the translator himself. So the importance compression as a potential of implementing the joint mission increases under prerequisites time deficit.

From a theoretical standpoint, compression in SI was once notably theorised in a seminal find out about by using Ghelly Chernov for whom it is a 'labour saving gadget in intense conditions of SI [that is made viable thanks] to the linguistic redundancy in the thematic factor of the discourse' (2004: 113). Such a commentary needs to be examined in larger element in view that it implies a variety of important notions that need to not be taken for granted:

- 1) compression in SI is actually possible;
- 2) it can be performed thanks to a certain diploma of redundancy in the source message;
- 3) it is labour saving system that helps interpreters handle speeches delivered at a fast rate.

The first two notions will be addressed in detail in the 2nd phase of this study, through the present literature, applicable examples and proof got from the study of a spoken corpus. The choice of a corpus-based approach responds to requirements set via contemporary lookup and is in line with tips via Robin Setton according to whom: 'as a first step towards perception deciphering processes ... it looks sensible to begin

¹ European Commission's Audiovisual Service. <http://ec.europa.eu/avservices/home> (Accessed 6

March 2009)

by looking at and evaluating the original discourse and its interpreted versions, rather of imposing fashions of memory and attention on the process, a priori' (2002: 29-30).

Syllabic compression

This compression mechanism takes area at the lowest stage and entails the preference of phrases that have fewer syllables than the ones in the SL.

Lexical compression

The second type of compression implies the use of 'fewer words to express the same idea.' (Chernov 2004: 115). Those who have some experience in editing or in the news sector will know that expressing a concept with as few words as possible is in fact a very complex art.

Syntactic compression

According to Chernov: Syntactic compression results from the choice of a shorter and simpler construction than that used in the original, for instance by a) breaking a complex sentence with involved clause structure into several simple sentences ... c) substituting a prepositional phrase for a participial construction) d) substituting a single word for a word combination, or an abbreviation or the full name of a country or an organisation, ex.

Situational compression refers to the 'elimination of speech chunks bearing information which is compensated for with the aid of the extra linguistic situation of the communication' (Shiryaev mentioned in Chernov 2004: 120). Being a approach that involves context it could well be the most bendy compression strategy. The following instance taken from the minutes of a UN meeting has often been quoted as a traditional example of ¹situational compression: 'I now give the flooring to the distinguished delegate of the United Republic of Tanzania', rendered in the TL via the interpreter just with the word 'Tanzania'.

This example can be fully understood only within the context of conferences involving many different languages all of which require an interpretation. To cater for such needs the equipment commonly used in SI has a number of different channels which can be employed to interpret from one language into a number of different ones.

Conclusion

Speech compression mostly is really carried out by synonymous or essentially close to them replacements of phrases and sentences shorter words, phrases and sentences, omitting segments that kind of duplicate the information generally contained in previous context, omission of semantic units, redundant in a specific situation of communication, and the omission of semantic units, redundant from the point of view of the task of communication (A.F Shiryaev, p.98), which kind of is quite significant.

¹ Seleskovitch, D. 1990. 'Teaching conference interpreting'. In Lambert, S., & Moser-Mercer, S.

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